

DIGITALIZATION PROCESSES AND TECHNOLOGIES IN ENSURING GREEN FINANCE AND REALIZING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGS)

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ABSTRACT

The world is evidencing digitalization in all business processes at a higher pace. People must be familiar with use of such technologies to avail services provided by business organizations. Services providing organizations such banks, insurance companies, logistics providers use technologies largely as those technologies help them in offering services at the lowest cost possible and gaining competitive edge in the market over other players through such value-added services being provided. The question remains unanswered for the people around the world is whether the intensive industrialization strategy being followed across the world by organizations both private and public sector, is making a society that is free from environmental hazards such polluted air, polluted water and contaminated products and services. Organizations both public and private sector, will to have give an assurance that investments made by them are eco-friendly and environment friendly, so any harm to environment is not happening. Though organizations are mandatorily being asked to report on their commitment towards achieving the sustainable development goals, a commitment from organizations in achieving those sustainable goals is the need of the hour.

Sustainability development goals can very well be achieved through investments in green projects. Green projects are financed by bankers and financial institutions; thus, financing is getting well-regulated and channelled well in achieving green returns on investments. Green returns is the greatest outcome in green finances. The need for green return is vital as world is facing many environmental threats such as polluted air, polluted water, contaminated sea resources etc.

The challenge for both public and private organizations is identifying projects that are eco-friendly and environmentally friendly. Sustainable reports are being generated by organizations on the projects they intend to invest and at the same time, if the government and other eco-friendly organizations come out with certain prescribed standards and KPIs for organizations to adhere to in evaluating the impacts of long-term investments to be committed.

Developing standards and KPIs is a long-term process and that needs consent of many stakeholders. To address the present challenge and to ensure effective green financing and green returns, organizations both public and private, banks, financial institutions, project management committees, sustainable development organizations at UN must all be connected through technologies such as Internet of Things (IOT), Artificial Intelligence, Data Analytics. By sharing data across networks and getting intensive evaluations by all those stakeholders or environmental regulators, green finance and green returns could be made as something possible in the digital world.

Keywords: Digital Technologies – IOT – Artificial Intelligence – Data Analytics - Sharing data - Environmental protection authorities worldwide – Green Returns – Green Finance

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1. INTRODUCTION

Green Finance is the need of the hour as the world is experiencing unusual issues such as COVID-19, spoiled water, lack of basic amenities in some part of the world, depleting land, and sea resources due to excessive pollution etc. Zadek and Flynn (2013)¹ define green finance as “it is often used interchangeably with green investment. Most obviously, it would include costs such as project preparation and land acquisition costs, both of which are not just significant but can pose distinct financing challenges.” Green finance is financing long-term and short-term projects that include acquisition of all potential resources needed for manufacturing and providing best possible services to the people, who would consume them at the end. Those projects must not be evaluated only from returns point of view but at the same time the impact these projects make on environmental factors such as land, water, air etc. Industrialization is the core for improving the GDP and inflationary pressure, at the same time the impact of industrialization on environmental factors must be carefully analysed so that true benefits of such green investments are realisable. For achieving such sustainable development goals, green finance, green investment, and green returns are mandatory. Evaluating projects that are expected to be contributing to achieving sustainable development goals is the highest priority for both public and private sector organizations and that needs an input from all stakeholders as well environmental protection authority worldwide. So, standards and KPIs are inevitable, and which can be well developed with the help of digital technologies such IOT, AI, Data analytics etc. Indirectly, green financing is well achieved through digitalization of data collection processes and evaluating projects against well-developed environmental KPIs and standards.

2. NEED FOR DIGITALIZATION IN GREEN FINANCE

The need for digitalization in Green Finance arises due to the following factors:

(i) Digitalization of financing processes gives large amount of data, thus evaluation of a project from all stakeholders including environmental authorities worldwide becomes easier and possible thing.

(ii) Environmental impact that green investments would produce over the long run can be well estimated as the data from all sources are accessible and available due to the presence of digital technologies in project evaluation processes. Those processes are well used by banks and financial institutions.

(iii) Digitalization reduces risks and uncertainties arising out of changes happening in environmental forces.

(iv) Chartered Banker (2023)² argues that green finance and sustainable finance are very important aspects to be looked at these days as these two will help nations in redirecting investments towards environmentally friendly projects and projects that integrate ESG factors into investment decision-making processes.

3. DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ARE THE ROUTE TO ACHIEVE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND GREEN FINANCING GOALS

Digital Technologies such as Internet of Things (IOT), Artificial Intelligence, Data Analytics are widely used by financing institutions including Banks worldwide for gathering and collecting essential data. IOT and Artificial Intelligence can help in gathering data and producing possible scenarios about the impact of green investment projects would make on environmental factors such as air, water, forests etc, so the decision making on investing in such projects would be made. The decision-making processes are widely supported and helped by digital technologies such IOT, AI and Data analytics. Blog.gft (2023)³ presents that digital technologies are helping companies and bankers the way they collect data, manage and store and turning them into an action-based business information, so decisions can be easily made.

4. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGS) AND SUSTAINABLE FINANCE INCLUDING GREEN FINANCE

Green investments are investments in financial securities such as stocks and bonds, that are offered by companies whose major goals are improving the environmental conditions (WGECO, 2024)⁴. The major challenge that every organization is facing in getting the required finances through green investment projects is lesser interest shown on such projects by financial institutions and the investing public due to the lower returns being dominating. Sachs I.D et.al (2019)⁵ argue that if sustainable development goals will have to be achieved, then there needs a big shift in financing processes, as banks and financial institutions will need policies and procedures directing them to fund environment friendly projects intensively than the other non-greener projects. Countries will have to intensify green financing and green financing instruments like stocks and bonds to progress well in SDGs attainment. Eco-friendly projects must be given due importance by the economies, so that green financing and green returns will become significant contributing forces in SDG focus.

Green finance contributes to achieving SDGs in the following ways:

(i) Sustainable development goals focus on attainment of certain actions that provide safe and green environment for the generations to come. To have an environment that are greener, safe and non-polluted, adequate care must be taken in making certain long-term projects. Projects that can be implemented and executed can be greener projects, so the welfare of environment is well taken care of and financing these projects will fall under green financing. Thus, green financing ultimately aims at realising SDGs.

(ii) Green financing creates a financial market for the instruments that aim at enhancing environmental forces. Thus, an investment culture is created in an economy wherein only greener projects are only considered for execution and non-greener projects are duly getting abandoned. This initiative will take an economy in greener paths and ensures attainment of SDGs.

(iii) Green financing creates an awareness about protecting the natural environment to the society. Institutional and individual investors will be highly motivated to invest their surpluses on green investments, thus making the economies to move successfully towards SDGs.

5. DIGITALIZATION FOR ACHIEVING SDGS AND GREEN INVESTMENTS/FINANCE

As economies keep moving ahead in developments, performing activities using digital technologies has become indispensable and vital. This offers voluminous benefits for both the organizations and economy (El Khoury et al., 2023)⁶. Economic progression is inevitable for economies, but capitalizing those benefits in a much greener ways is the ultimate challenge and achievement. Economies must start floating policies and procedures that can be adopted in all marketplaces, which addressing the harmful impacts of non-greener approaches and benefits of greener approaches. Digitalization is the pathway for achieving higher investments in green projects and related SDGs. Organizations, both large and small, must focus on their capital investment and working capital decisions in order to contribute in the green initiative of an economy and participate activity green investments, assuring green returns for their investors.

The following diagram illustrates how green investments/finance help organizations in formulating strategic plans and investment policies:

Diagram 1. Reflecting use of Digital Technologies and its impact on green investments evaluation process and achieving SDGs through Strategic plans

The above diagram illustrates how organizations can improve their operational processes through digitalization and how digital technologies employed could inculcate the greener investment culture within an organization. The benefits of using digital technologies in achieving SDGs and greener investments can be:

- (i) Organizations need speed up their digitalization processes since it offers numerous benefits such as improved operational efficiency, cost control and reduction, timely delivery of value to customers, enhanced effectiveness in meeting customer expectations etc.
- (ii) Digital technologies can help organization in collecting, analysing, presenting data and make good and appropriate eco-friendly decisions.
- (iii) Digital Technologies motivate organizations to perform their processes in a more innovative ways, thus inculcating the culture wherein innovation as predominant. Innovation can be one of organization's key and routine tasks. This is highly possible through digitalization. Digitalization brings out the organization's potential in evaluating various investment projects, including green investments and green financing. Thus, digitalization makes an organization, an SDG oriented.
- (iv) With the help of digital technologies, organizations can evaluate about their achievements and progression made in fulfilling their SDGs. This motivates organizations to look in for green investments and greener returns.

- (v) Digital technologies can be widely used in evaluating capital investment projects Long-term investments are made after carefully analysing cash inflows and cash outflows associated with those projects. When organizations are in possession of digital technologies needed for estimating cash inflows and outflows, then it becomes easy for them to include certain other components in analysis. Impact of investments on natural resources, human resources and other national resources can be included in the analysis and accordingly, appropriate green investment decisions can be made.

6. TRANSFORMATION FROM CONVENTIONAL INVESTMENTS PERSPECTIVE TO GREEN INVESTMENTS PERSPECTIVE

Greenbank investments (2024)⁷ explains that green investments are investments that aims to generate returns through investments made in organizations and business processes that are environment friendly. Organizations prefer to invest in projects that yield greater returns. Such organizations must be motivated enough to go in for investing in ventures and business that are environment friendly. This transformation will happen provided green investments are widely practised and green returns become a predominant return in the financial markets. Due to the risk involved in such green investment projects and the lower returns generated, organizations neglect such investments. The economies must formulate policies, regulations for companies to promote green investment projects, so the issues like lower returns and high rate of risk will not become some of the common characteristics of green investments. Perspectives of organizations can be shifted through state's involvement. This can be affected through formulating priorities and policies that promises greener economy.

7. DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES THAT CAN ENSURE GREEN FINANCE/RETURNS

Some of the technologies that can assist organizations in evaluating investment projects well are presented as below:

Table 1 - Table presenting the various digital technologies and their usefulness in evaluating investment projects, both traditional and green

Sl. No	Digital Technology	Specific characteristics of the technology	Usefulness in evaluating an investment choice	Usefulness in evaluating a green investment option
1	Cloud Computing	Voluminous data that can be stored without investing much on data storing assets	Huge volume of financial data can be collected and analysed to present a recommendation	Voluminous financial and non-financial data can be stored in clouds for analysing the impact of projects on the environmental factors as well
2	Artificial Intelligence	Sophisticated evaluation of various financial and non-financial variables such as cash flow, market share, employee performance etc.	Intensive analysis on financial and non-financial aspects of a projects. Better recommendation can be arrived out using AI.	Green Projects can be well examined by having an artificial scenario. It provides an in-depth analysis through presenting a solution for an imaginary scenario. Green factors

3	Big Data and Analytics	Vast amount of data can be collected, stored and analysed so an appropriate decision can be made	Huge amount of data on financial and non-financial aspects can be collected. A detailed analysis and report can be prepared	Green factors can be fed into the system and appropriate analysis can be made. A detailed analysis on contributions of a project on green factors can be made
4	Edge Computing	Data can be analysed at the point of source itself.	Data can be collected and analysed at point of origin itself. It presents a comprehensive analysis	Green contributions can be ascertained in detail as the data is collected at the source point itself. Impact factor can be analysed well.
5	Robotic Process Automation	Data entry can be done using robots	Data collection and analysis can be automated. Good analysis is the main feature.	Automated Process will collect data about environmental impact and present a good recommendation
6	Blockchain Technology	It is distributed ledger, wherein blocks are continuously getting added across the network	Real time data is used in evaluation of long-term capital investments	Real time data is used extensively in analysis and a detailed meaningful real time data based reports can be developed, accordingly, crucial green investment decisions can be made.

8. Blockchain: Enabling Green Finance

As the world grapples with the urgent need to transition towards a more sustainable and low-carbon economy, blockchain's inherent characteristics, such as transparency, traceability, and immutability, make it a promising tool for enabling green finance (Kouhizadeh & Sarkis, 2018; Kshetri, 2021; Mukhtar et al., 2019)^{8, 9 & 10}

One of the key advantages of blockchain in the realm of green finance is its ability to enhance transparency and accountability throughout the supply chain. By providing a tamper-proof and decentralized record of transactions, blockchain can help businesses and consumers alike to track the environmental impact of their activities, from resource extraction to product distribution. This level of visibility can empower stakeholders to make informed decisions, fostering a more sustainable and eco-friendly supply chain ecosystem.

Moreover, blockchain's decentralized nature and smart contract functionality can facilitate the development of innovative financial instruments and mechanisms that directly support environmentally friendly initiatives. For instance, blockchain-based platforms can enable the tokenization of carbon credits, allowing for the seamless trading and tracking of these assets, which are crucial for incentivizing and rewarding sustainable practices.

Furthermore, blockchain-enabled solutions can address the challenges associated with high costs and technological limitations that often hinder the adoption of sustainable practices, particularly in developing countries. By reducing transaction costs and enhancing the efficiency of resource management, blockchain can make green finance more accessible and scalable, enabling the participation of a wider range of stakeholders.

9. Sustainability Accounting – An Evaluation of actions for achieving SDGs through ESG reports

Mid and West (2024)¹¹ explains that “In business and policy contexts, sustainability seeks to prevent the depletion of natural or physical resources, so that they will remain available for the long term”. An ESG report is prepared and presented about Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) impacts made due to their business activities. The purposes of preparing such ESG reports can be summarized as follows:

The purposes of ESG reporting include:

- (i) presenting what corporates are doing to protect environmental factors
- (ii) Informing investors about their social responsibilities and what they had done for the society’s well-being
- (iii) Showing how they comply with various governance norms and regulations

ESG reporting is making people know about corporate’s involvement in achieving their environmental, social and governance goals. It is reporting of ESG activities with data. Corporate’s ESG activities are reported with data, so those activities initiated are regarded as real by the viewers of such data.

These are important because,

(i) Organizations are using resources to meet their goals. Thus, one of the goals that they must pursue is utilizing resources more responsibly, so such activities are not causing severe damage to environmental forces.

(ii) ESG is a reporting framework, it is more relevant to publicly traded companies looking to attract investors and inform investors about their ESG involvement, so financing their activities becomes accessible.

(iii) Sustainable Investments is the key for longevity of an organization. Sustainable finance is about including environmental, social and governance considerations in investment decisions, (a) Green finance and green returns can be the most appropriate yardsticks for evaluating the long –term investments and (b) non-financial considerations such as compliance with norms, legal requirements, interests of stakeholders must also be considered in evaluating long-term investments

10. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

Organizations must be socially responsible and meeting the expectations of the society. Organizations are existing not only for making profits and losses, but they are also part of the society, contributing significantly to the welfare of the people and natural resources. Earth is having enormous resources like plants, trees, air, water etc and these resources must be protected well so that generations will keep using them. Sustainable development goals have been developed by the UN and been asking nations to work on achieving them. Sustainable development goals attainment involves series of actions planned and executed by companies, individuals and the government. Thus, everyone in the society must contribute to achieving those SDGs. Singh (2022)¹² et. al. present that India is growing at a faster rate economically due to the stress given for the sustainable development and not on the industrialization only.

Organizations must now seriously consider greener aspects of their business activities. It can be financing, investment and dividend decision, all must have to be green. Organizations must give focus on investing funds in projects that focus on developing/sustaining environmental factors. Business activities must not be harmful and damaging the existing resources. Such projects must be given due consideration by the organizations and the government. This approach will facilitate organizations and the government to move towards fulfilling those SDG based targets.

To move towards greener, organizations must seriously give time and efforts in financial engineering aspects that would produce green investments and green returns. Higher returns and minimum risks can also be guaranteed in such green investments. The economic growth must accompany a series of effort exerted for the welfare of the natural resources. This process can be further simplified if organizations work on digitalization and digital transformation. Ruman et al. (2022)¹³ demonstrate that small and micro enterprises are playing an important role in financial innovation and sustainable development with green financial products that are getting developed using emerging financial digital technologies.

Digital technologies provide a greater opportunity for the organizations to excel in their business processes and extract greater benefits out of it. Digital technologies can be used well in collecting, analysing and presenting the data in a more useful manner, so all decisions both long-term and short-term can be made with caution and considering all the relevant and important factors. Thus, digitalization makes organizations socially responsible and focused on SDGs. SDGs must be the vision and mission for every organization. Achieving SDGs must be the core objectives of an organization. Strategic plans of an organization must provide a better scope for including SDGs, so companies can achieve twin goals such as making profits and providing the better health to the natural resources.

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